

Free-Energy Change of Exchange Reactions

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The free-energy change of ion-exchange reactions in clays has been determined at different temperatures with Padogaon and aquagel Ca-form of membranes by measuring the potential difference between two electrolytes separated by the membrane. The temperature coefficient of E.M.F. is nearly the same for the two membranes, but varies with the activity of the cation pairs. The heat of exchange reactions, ΔH , calculated by using the Gibbs-Helmholtz equation, varies with the cation pair, but for the same pair i , remains almost constant at the different temperature and activity ranges studied. It is peculiar that ΔH value for K—Na pair is much higher than that of either the Mg—K and Ca—K pairs.

According to the theory as proposed by Marshall¹ to interpret electrochemical behaviour of mineral membranes, the membrane in addition to possessing exchange property is supposed to act as a reversible electrode system with respect to the cationic solution in contact with it. The exchange of a surface cation for another in the solution is attended with heat changes, *i.e.*, the cationic bonding energy, the amount of which will depend on the cation and mineral characteristics of the membrane. For a passage of one faraday of electricity through a cell of the type:

the total potential measured will be

$$E_{\text{obs}} = \Delta G + \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{a_1}{a_2} + \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{a_1(\text{Cl}^-)}{a_2(\text{Cl}^-)}$$

where ΔG in calories may be considered as difference between the bonding energies of potassium and sodium ion, which is also the difference in free-energy change for such exchange reactions. The total potential includes the potential due to difference in chloride ion activities in the two solutions. For divalent (a_1)—monovalent (a_2) cell, the expression would be

$$E_{\text{obs}} = \Delta G + \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{a_1^{\frac{1}{2}}}{a_2} + \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{2a_1(\text{Cl}^-)}{a_2(\text{Cl}^-)}$$

and for divalent-divalent cell,

$$E_{\text{obs}} = \Delta G + \frac{RT}{2F} \ln \frac{a_1}{a_2} + \frac{RT}{F} \ln \frac{a_1(\text{Cl}^-)}{a_2(\text{Cl}^-)}$$

To identify the free-energy change, calculated from E. M. F. measurement, with the difference in heat change of exchange reactions, it is necessary to assume that the temperature coefficient of the E.M.F. is either zero or negligibly small. Banerjee² showed, however, that

1. *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1948, 52, 1294.

2. *J. Indian Soc. Soil Sci.*, 1956, 4, 221.

this is not so using soft clay plugs. The clay plugs register under suitable conditions reversible potentials in the same manner as the membrane electrode³. The advantage of the plugs is that these attain equilibrium quickly. It is also known that ΔH for such exchange reactions with a cationic pair, say Ca—K, remains almost constant within an appreciable temperature range⁴. Similar experiments have been carried out with membrane electrodes, the results of which are reported here.

EXPERIMENTAL

The experimental set up was similar to those mentioned earlier⁴. Only Padegaon and aquagel Ca-form membranes were used. The entire cell, composed of the membrane electrode with two identical Ag, AgCl electrodes in the two solutions separated by the membrane, was placed in a thermostat adjusted to the desired temperature. Precautions were taken to prevent evaporation of the solution. The F.M.F. after thermal equilibrium was measured after ascertaining any asymmetry potential. The concentrations of the electrolytes were kept within the range in which membrane electrodes obeyed the Nernst equation. The measurements were made with the following pairs: K—Na, Ca—K, Mg—K, Mg—Ca. The results are recorded in Tables I-IX. Usually the average of four sets of readings, not differing by more than 0.5 mv, is recorded in the tables.

DISCUSSION

Tables I-III show the measurements with the Na—K pair, in which α_K was kept the same at 0.009, whereas α_{Na} was varied from 0.00877 to 0.0263. The temperature coefficient of E.M. F. is negative, indicating an increase of entropy with increase of temperature. The enthalpy changes involved in the exchange of Na for K, as recorded by the two electrodes, viz., those prepared from Padegaon clay and aquagel, are more or less constant within the temperature and concentration ranges studied. The difference observed between the two electrodes, which is maintained in the case of other pairs at all the concentrations studied, is perhaps characteristic of the exchange behaviour of the clays themselves in the form of the membranes.

TABLE I

$$\frac{\text{Inside}}{\text{Outside}} \frac{\alpha_K}{\alpha_{Na}} = \frac{0.009}{0.00877} \quad (\text{outside +ve observed}).$$

$$[d(\Delta G)/dT = -4 \text{ cal./deg.}^\circ]$$

P=Padegaon Ca-form. A=aquagel Ca-form.

Temp.	Obs. E.M.F. (mv).		$\Delta G (H_K - H_{Na} \text{ (cals.)})$		$\Delta H \text{ (cals.)}$	
	P.	A.	P.	A.	P.	A.
25°	22.3	14.2	493	325	1686	1517
35°	21.4	13.2	404	218	1696	1514
45°	20.0	11.8	418	250	1690	1522
60°	18.1	7.6	350	175	1683	1507

3. Mukherjee and Marshall, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1951, 55, 81.

4. Adhikari, *this Journal*, 1961, 38, 817.

TABLE II

$$\frac{\text{Inside } a_{\text{K}}}{\text{Outside } a_{\text{Na}}} = \frac{0.009}{0.00292} \text{ (outside +ve observed).}$$

$$[d(\Delta G)/dT = -5 \text{ cal./deg.}^\circ].$$

Temp.	Obs. E.M.F. (mv). Membrane.		$\Delta G(H_{\text{K}} - H_{\text{Na}})$ (cal.).		ΔH (cal.).	
	P.	A.	P.	A.	P.	A.
	30°	64.2	60.00	97	1.1	1612
35°	63.8	59.55	66	-30	1606	1510
45°	63.1	58.80	11	-95	1601	1495
55°	62.3	58.10	-48	-143	1592	1497
60°	62.0	57.75	-71	-165	1594	1500

TABLE III

$$\frac{\text{Inside } a_{\text{K}}}{\text{Outside } a_{\text{Na}}} = \frac{0.009}{0.0263} \text{ (outside -ve observed).}$$

$$[d(\Delta G)/dT = -4.3 \text{ cal./deg.}^\circ].$$

Temp.	Obs. E.M.F. (mv). Membrane.		$\Delta G(H_{\text{K}} - H_{\text{Na}})$ (cal.).		ΔH (cal.).	
	P.	A.	P.	A.	P.	A.
	30°	-43.6	-50.0	312	158	1615
35°	-45.4	-52.2	293	136	1616	1460
45°	-49.3	-56.1	246	89	1613	1456
55°	-53.0	-59.6	204	52	1614	1482

In Tables IV and V are recorded the data for the Ca-K pair at two different concentrations. Here also the constancy of ΔH values within the range of temperature and concentration studied is to be noted.

TABLE IV

$$\frac{\text{Inside } a_{\text{K}}}{\text{Outside } a_{\text{Ca}}} = \frac{0.009}{0.0027} \text{ (outside +ve observed).}$$

$$[d(\Delta G)/dT = -6 \text{ cal./deg.}^\circ].$$

Temp.	Obs. E.M.F. (mv). Membrane.		ΔG (cal.). ($H_{\frac{1}{2}\text{Ca}} - H_{\text{K}}$).		ΔH (cal.).	
	P.	A.	P.	A.	P.	A.
	25°	24.5	18.5	-424	-563.0	1363
35°	23.4	17.5	-494	-620.0	1364	1228
45°	22.2	16.4	-546	-678.0	1361	1230
50°	21.7	15.7	-572	-710.0	1366	1228
60°	20.4	14.2	-636	-778.5	1362	1230

TABLE V

$$\frac{\text{Inside}}{\text{Outside}} \frac{a_K}{a_{Ca}} = \frac{0.009}{0.0081} \quad (\text{Outside + ve observed}).$$

$$[d(\Delta G)/dT = -8 \text{ cal./deg.}^\circ].$$

Temp.	Obs. E.M.F. (mv). Membrane.		ΔG (cals.) ($H_{\frac{1}{2}Ca} - H_K$).		ΔH (cals.).	
	P.	A.	P.	A.	P.	A.
35°	45.2	40.5	-1103	-1213	1363	1251
40°	45.0	40.2	-1140	-1250	1364	1254
50°	44.5	39.6	-1223	-1330	1361	1248
60°	43.9	39.0	-1303	-1410	1363	1245

It is surprising that the difference in ΔH , which may be considered as a measure of the difference in bonding energies of the cation pair concerned, is greater in the case of Na—K than Ca—K or Mg—K (Table VIII). The ΔH of the Ca—Mg pair is similarly (Table VI, VII) much less than that of the Na—K pair. The difference between the ΔH values of the Ca—K pair (Table V) and of the Mg—K pair (Table VIII) may be compared with the ΔH values obtained from measurements with the Ca—Mg pair (Table VI). The values shown in the last two columns of Table IX are of the same order and vary within 16%.

TABLE VI

$$\frac{\text{Inside}}{\text{Outside}} \frac{a_{Ca}}{a_{Mg}} = \frac{0.0081}{0.0081} \quad (\text{Outside - ve observed}).$$

$$[d(\Delta G)/dT = -3.5 \text{ cal./deg.}^\circ].$$

Temp.	Obs. E.M.F. Membrane. P.	ΔG . ($H_{Ca} - H_{Mg}$)	ΔH .
50°	-5.75	-416	655
60°	-5.50	-453	712

TABLE VII

$$\frac{\text{Inside}}{\text{Outside}} \frac{a_{Ca}}{a_{Mg}} = \frac{0.0081}{0.0027} \quad (\text{Outside + ve observed}).$$

$$[d(\Delta G)/dT = -3.2 \text{ cal./deg.}^\circ].$$

Temp.	Obs. E.M.F. Membrane. P.	ΔG ($H_{Ca} - H_{Mg}$).	ΔH .
50°	50.1	191	839
60°	51.0	231	836

TABLE VIII

Temp.	Obs. E.M.F. Membrane. P	$\Delta G(H_{\frac{1}{2}Mg}-H_K)$	ΔH .
35°	508.00 mv	-971 cal.	1000 cal.
50°	51.15	-1069	998
60°	51.00	-1131	1000

TABLE IX

Temp.	$\Delta G(H_{\frac{1}{2}Ca}-H_K)^*$	$\Delta G(H_{\frac{1}{2}Mg}-H_K)^{**}$	$\Delta G(H_{\frac{1}{2}Ca}-H_{\frac{1}{2}Mg})^\dagger$		$\Delta H \text{ (calc.)}$	
			Obs.	Calc. (a-b)	Obs.‡	Calc.
35°	-1103 cal.	-971 cal.	-182 cal.	-132 cal.	434	363
50°	-1223	-1069	-208	-154	439	363
60°	-1303	1131	-227	-172	439	363

* cf. Table V (a).

** cf. Table VIII (b).

† cf. Table VI.

‡ cf. Table VI.

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